

Studies in Photo-Chemical Reactions. Part III. The Influence of Polarised Radiations on Certain Photo-Chemical Reactions.

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Semmens (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 954) found that the hydrolysis of starch grains proceeds much more rapidly in polarised light than in heterogeneous light. Baly and Semmens (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1924, 97B, 250) noticed that plane polarised light caused a marked acceleration in seed germination and formation of flower but no effect was observed on vegetative growth. They also showed that starch was completely hydrolysed in weak diastase solution when exposed to polarised light, while only a slight serration of the grains took place in ordinary light.

Jones (*Ann. Bot.*, 1925, 39, 651) was unable to repeat the experiments on the hydrolysis of starch in the presence of gelatine solution. Baly and Semmens (*Nature*, Dec. 5, 1925, 817) attributed this failure to an experimental defect in Jones's experiments.

Recently Semmens repeated her experiments on the hydrolysis of starch in small flasks using light polarised by the scattering of colloidal particles of taka-diastase and she again got positive results. Bhatnagar and Lall (*Nature*, 27th Feb., 1926) showed that *V. cholerae* and *B. typhosus* grow more rapidly in polarised light than in ordinary light of the same intensity.

Experiments on the effects of polarised radiations on metabolic activity in rabbits and guinea-pigs by the same workers along with Mathur yielded exactly similar results. On this basis they gave a theory of the rise in temperature in the afternoon in normal individuals as well as in certain pathological conditions (*Nature*, 3rd July, 1926, 11).

In light of the above facts, it becomes important to examine whether the character of light with respect to its state of polarisation has any effect on photo-chemical reactions.

It is generally recognised that the frequency and intensity both affect the photo-chemical equilibrium, but the role of polarisation has not been studied except by Weigert (*Ber. deutsch. Phys. Ges.*, 1919, 21, 482), and Zocher and Coper (*Sitzungsber. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1925, 23, 426). Cotton and Mouton also showed that the absorption of the two components of circularly polarised light by copper tartrate differ considerably.

Investigations on the above lines evidently ought to give valuable information regarding the mechanism of the photo-chemical reactions, and if the results obtained are similar to what has been observed in the case of certain bio-chemical reactions, it will be possible to apply the knowledge obtained from the latter experiments to the elucidation of the former, as the chemical reactions studied here are certainly simpler and better understood than the complex bio-chemical reactions studied by previous investigators.

Since the well-known photo-chemical reactions can be divided into two classes, *viz.* (1) reactions which constitute homogeneous systems and (2) reactions constituting heterogeneous systems, it was considered desirable to include in the present investigation examples from both the classes.

The following reactions were chosen as representing the first class:—

(i) The reduction of mercuric chloride to calomel by ammonium oxalate in presence of light, which proceeds according to the following equation:

Winther (*Zeit. Wissen. Phot.*, 1909, 7, 409) has shown that the light sensitivity of this reaction is accelerated by ferric ions.

(ii) The change of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid in acetone solution.

(iii) The photo-decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.

Of the second class of photo-chemical reactions the interaction between water and liquid amalgams of sodium and potassium was chosen. These reactions have been shown to be photo-sensitive by Bhatnagar, Parshad and Mukherjee (*This Journal*, 1924, 1, 263).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The polarising apparatus essentially consisted of two wooden chambers, one of which was fixed in position, while the other could be slid towards the fixed one or away from it on a base. The

base itself consisted of three plane pieces joined by means of two pairs of hinges, in such a way that the three parts could be folded on themselves. The top of the fixed chamber could be opened like the lid of a box, and from the near sides the boxes communicated with each other. The front of both the boxes was pierced by a hole 7 cm. in diameter to which two thin iron cylinders 14 cm. in length were attached. These cylinders served to lead the beams to the two reaction chambers, which were small wooden boxes covered all over with black paper, and the reaction vessels were placed inside these boxes to protect them from outside radiations. At the back of the fixed chamber was attached firmly an electric bulb. A hole was bored through the back of the movable box so that light could enter through it. Twenty-one glass plates were set in frame placed in the box. This frame could be rotated and the plates could be fixed at the desired angle. The two boxes could be brought near or taken apart without affecting the angle at which the plates were once arranged. When not in use the boxes were moved apart to their farthest ends and the base was folded, so that the whole thing could be converted into a big box.

A Fixed box. G Glass plates. C Absorption Cell.
 B Movable box. P Reflecting plates. V Reaction Vessels.

Fig. 1.

The various parts of the apparatus in Fig. 1 are self-explanatory. Some plates were placed in the fixed box to equalise the intensities of the two beams so got. Thin plates of ground glass were placed in the path of the rays to make the beams homogeneous in intensity.

Two cells full of alum solution were interposed in the path of the beams to absorb the heat rays. The intensities of the beams were equalised by a sensitive thermopile and Broca galvanometer.

It was noted by means of a sensitive thermometer that the temperatures of the two beams were taken to see if a particular wavelength was missing in any of them.

Source of Light.—Ordinary 220 volts electric bulbs of 500 to 2000 c.p. were used according to the requirements of the experiment.

Polarisation.—The percentage polarisation of light depends upon the number of glass plates used and the angle at which the incident rays fall upon them

The method used in measuring the percentage polarisation consisted in compensating the polarisation by means of one or more inclined glass plates

Seven glass plates were placed between the polarised source of light and the Savart plate with its analysing nicol

The Savart plate consists of a plane parallel plate cut from a quartz crystal at an angle of 45° to the optic axis. The plate is then sectioned parallel to the plane surface, one half is rotated through 90° relative to the other and the two are cemented together.

“ The glass plates are rotated until the Savart fringes disappear, i.e., until the polarisation produced by transmission through the oblique plates exactly compensates the opposite polarisation originally present in the source. The angle θ through which the plates have been turned is read (cf. “Physical Optics” by R. W. Wood, pp 298-299)

If the angle of incidence upon the inclined plate is θ and the refractive index of glass is μ , we can calculate ϕ , the angle of refraction from

$$\frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \phi} = \mu \text{ (refractive index) } "$$

Brewster found that the index of refraction was the tangent of the angle of maximum polarisation, which in the case of glass is 57.5° .

“ From the theory of reflection we have for the ratio of the amplitude of the vibration perpendicular to the plane of incidence to that in the plane, for transmission through the two surfaces of a plate

$$\cos^2 (\theta - \phi)$$

the intensity ratio will be the square of this, or

$$\cos^4 (\theta - \phi)$$

If we have n plates the intensity ratio will be equal to $\cos^{4n}(\theta - \phi)$ ”

Suppose we get $\cos^4(\theta - \phi) = 1/x$,

then percentage polarisation = $\frac{x-1}{x+1} \times 100$

In the experiment $\theta = 60.50$, percentage polarisation = 88.3

The Chemicals — The chemicals used were all Merck's extra pure quality

For the first reactions, namely the reduction of mercuric chloride by ammonium oxalate, saturated solutions of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and HgCl_2 were prepared in distilled water and stored in coloured bottles. The strengths of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and HgCl_2 solutions were 28.5 and 38.6 g per litre respectively. The progress of the reactions could be studied by (1) comparing the volume of CO_2 gas evolved during the exposure in the two gases, or (2) by estimating the amounts of mercurous chloride precipitated in the two similar samples exposed to the two beams. As for the first method the volume of CO_2 evolved by the source of light used was found to be too little to saturate the solutions and then to indicate changes of volumes in the two capillary tubes attached to the reaction vessels and consequently the second method was adopted.

Thirty c.c. of HgCl_2 solution were mixed with 30 c.c. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ solution in a coloured bottle, 1 c.c. of 2N FeCl_3 was added and the whole was shaken.

Twenty-five c.c. of this mixture were taken in each test tube which were exposed to the two beams. After a definite interval of time the exposure was stopped and the contents of both the test tubes were filtered in two Gooch crucibles having asbestos pulp as the filtering materials. The crucibles were previously washed, dried in steam oven and weighed. The precipitates were washed till free from chlorides. They were then dried in the steam oven.

and weighed till the weights were constant. The amounts of precipitates formed during the exposure were thus estimated. Some of the results are given below :—

TABLE I.

Time of exposure.	Amount of precipitate in m. gms obtained by exposure to polarised light.	Amount of precipitate in m.gms. got by exposure to unpolarised light.	Difference.
4 hours.	2.7	2.7	...
5 ..	2.9	3.0	- .1
7½ ..	4.4	4.8	+ .1
11 ..	7.0	7.2	- .2
16 ..	10.1	10.2	- .1
24 ..	14.3	14.2	+ .1

TABLE II.

Reaction vessels interchanged.

4½ hours,	2.8	2.7	+ .1
7½ ..	4.2	4.4	- .2
8 ..	4.5	4.4	+ .1
11 ..	6.8	7.0	- .2
16 ..	10.3	10.4	- .1
24 ..	14.4	14.2	+ .2

An examination of the tables above will show that the amounts of precipitates obtained in both the beams are equal in all these experiments within the limits of experimental error, showing that both the beams are equally active in accelerating this reaction.

Reaction No. II.—The photo-decomposition of H_2O_2 is accelerated by alkalis and NaOH was therefore used as catalyst. Twenty-five c.c. of a 10 vol. strength solution of H_2O_2 , (Merck's) were mixed with 25 c.c. of distilled water in a coloured bottle, 5 c.c. of 5 N NaOH added and the whole was thoroughly shaken.

Twenty-five c.c. of this mixture were taken by means of a dry pipette in the two test tubes which were placed in the boxes covered

black. Just before exposure samples were drawn from the two and their permanganate values were determined by titrations. As the exposure proceeded samples were again drawn from time to time and titrated in the same way. The results obtained are embodied in the following tables:—

TABLE III.

	<i>Polarised beam.</i>		<i>Unpolarised beam.</i>	
Time of exposure from the start.	Vol. of KMnO ₄ used for samples.	Decrease in permanganate value due to decomposition.	KMnO ₄ used for corresponding samples.	Decrease in permanganate value due to decomposition.
..	15.0 c.c.	..	15.0 c.c.	.
1 hour.	12.7 ..	2.3	12.8 ..	2.2
1½ ..	12.0 ..	3.0	12.2 ..	2.8
2½ ..	11.3 ..	3.7	11.4 ..	3.6
4 ..	10.5 ..	4.4	10.8 ..	4.2
5 ..	10.2 ..	4.8	10.2 ..	4.8
6 ..	9.8 ..	5.2	9.9

TABLE IV.

The vessels interchanged.

..	14.4 c.c.	.	14.4 c.c.	..
1½ hours.	13.3 ..	1.1	13.3 ..	1.15
2½ ..	12.4 ..	2.0	12.4 ..	2.05
5 ..	11.55 ..	2.85	11.6 ..	2.85
6½ ..	10.8 ..	3.6	10.8 ..	3.65
7½ ..	10.15 ..	4.25	10.2 ..	4.25
8½ ..	9.6 ..	4.8	9.6 ..	4.85

The figures in the columns No. 3 and 5 of the above tables are very nearly equal in all cases and as they correspond to the decomposition of HO₂ by the two beams respectively, it is evident that in this case also polarised and unpolarised beams of equal intensity accelerate the reaction to an equal extent,

Heterogeneous Systems.

Reaction No. III.—The liquid amalgams of sodium and potassium react with water to produce hydrogen and their hydroxide even in the dark, but the reaction proceeds very much more vigorously in light and the velocity of the reaction can be measured fairly easily and accurately (1) by measuring the amount of hydrogen evolved and (2) by titrating the alkalis produced against standard acid. Both the methods have been employed in this investigation.

The amalgams were prepared by the electrolytic method of Richards (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 601).

The amalgam was then dried and transferred to the storing vessel which consisted of a big separating funnel fitted with a rubber cork. It was connected to a hydrogen generator through a soda-lime tower, and a sulphuric acid gas-washing bottle. The washing bottle also communicated with another vessel meant for taking out the amalgam in a current of hydrogen. The whole apparatus was completely covered with black paper to prevent the amalgams from being exposed to light.

The polarising apparatus was so designed that the whole arrangement could be turned through a right angle so that the electric vector vibrated at right angles to the plane of incidence. The results of these investigations have appeared in *Science* (Oct. 14th, 1927) and the details are described in a paper shortly appearing in the *Zeit. Phys. Chem.*

It is found that the perpendicularly polarised light accelerates the reaction considerably more than heterogeneous light, while the reaction is considerably less in parallel polarised light as compared to ordinary light. These results are analogous to the effect of polarised radiations on the photo-electric effect of these amalgams.

Discussion of Results.

As far as the results of the present investigation go, the following conclusions may be drawn from the same:—

1. Photo-chemical reactions in homogeneous systems are not sensitive to the state of polarisation of light.

2. In photo-chemical reactions constituting heterogeneous systems the state of polarisation of the radiant energy may have a selective effect.

In connection with the selective effect of polarised light on sodium and potassium amalgam it is interesting to recall the remarkable discovery of Elster and Geitel (*Weid. Ann. Physik*, 1894, **52**, 540) namely that the number of electrons liberated from a liquid alloy of sodium when exposed to light is much greater when the electric vector vibrates in the plane of incidence. These observations of Elster and Geitel have been confirmed by various workers notably by Pringsheim and Pohl.

The velocity and number of the electrons produced by light would determine the rate of photo-chemical reactions. The experiments of Elster and Geitel and Pohl and Pringsheim have established that the number of electrons liberated from these amalgams is much greater when the electric vector of the polarised light is vibrating in the plane of incidence. Hence it is natural to expect that the reaction between the amalgams and water will become accelerated under these conditions. These experiments constitute the first direct example of chemical reactions sensitive to the state of polarisation of the reacting light—the experiments of Weigert and Zocher (*loc. cit.*) being indirectly indicative of the same effect.

It is interesting to note here that Zocher and Weigert could prepare an optically active substance by the action of circularly polarised light on colloidal systems only. There is a certain amount of close similarity between their conclusions and the bearing of them on the results obtained here. It is also interesting to recall the failure of Ghosh and Mukherjee (this *Journal*, 1925, **2**, 165) to obtain a selective effect of polarised light on the photo-bromination of tartaric acid in aqueous solution. As the reaction studied by them constitutes a homogeneous system, it falls in line with our observations and confirms our conclusions.

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